

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Maharjan****FIRST NAME: Neha****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MS Word 365, Windows 8

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the main purpose of an academic essay?

- To persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.¹**
- To entertain the audience.
- To present a collection of quotes written by other researchers.
- To build your portfolio.

2. What are the stages of a writing process?

- Prewriting, writing, revising, editing, and publishing.²**
- Writing, editing, and publishing.
- Brainstorming, organizing, writing, and editing.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

² Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning* (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 6.

Prewriting, writing, and publishing.

3. **What information is vital for persuasive essays?**

Broad and general idea.

Evidence and facts.³

Strong and offensive language.

First-person “I” statements.

4. **What do researchers rely on to guide their investigation?**

Daily news.

Personal judgment.

Working hypothesis.⁴

A broad set of ideas.

5. **What information should be avoided in research papers?**

Evidence and facts.

Anecdotal information.⁵

Citations.

Objective information.

3 Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer, *Write Source 2000*, 115.

4 Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eight Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C Booth et al., 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 27.

5 Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 6.

6. **When can a research paper have sentences in the present tense?**
- Presenting generally accepted facts.⁶**
 - Deriving information from past research.
 - Presenting a fact that is no longer considered true.
 - Describing the methodology of research.
7. **What are the components required in the body paragraph of an essay?**
- Topic sentence, supporting sentences, evidence, and analysis.⁷**
 - Topic sentence and evidence.
 - Topic sentence, supporting sentences, and figures.
 - Supporting sentences, figures, and evidence.
8. **What is a rule relating to adding quotations in an essay?**
- For quotations five lines or longer, display it as a block quotation, without quotation marks.⁸**
 - For quotations five lines or longer, display it in text and use quotation marks.
 - Never use quotations that are five lines or longer.
 - For quotations five lines or longer, writers do not need to cite the source.
9. **Which format does WHO follow for dates?**

6 Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4, 5*.

7 Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 3*.

8 Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eight Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 208.

- Day, month, year with no commas (5 February 2021).⁹**
- Year, month, day with “slash” (2021/2/5).
- Month, day with no commas (February 5).
- Month, day, year with “slash” (02/05/2021).

10. **What is an example of a non-sexist language where a sex-specific description is avoided?**

- The female doctors conducted their morning rounds.
- The supervisor organized a team meeting.¹⁰**
- The male nurse checked the patient’s blood pressure.
- She dislikes her male boss.

⁹ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Malta: Marketing and Dissemination, 2004), 7.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 57.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Malta: Marketing and Dissemination, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.